

Diet and Bladder Pathophysiology

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ABSTRACT

The role that dietary factors play in the etiology of various diseases including overactive bladder syndrome (OAB), lower urinary tract syndrome (LUTS), and other urinary tract disorders is very important. The urinary bladder is an essential component of the genitourinary system that is adapted for reception, storage and excretion of large amounts of urine. Any disorder affecting the bladder negatively impacts an individual's quality of life. There is an increasing incidence of urinary tract disorders, and this comes with the need to understand the influence of external factors/choices, in this case diet, on the structure and function of bladder. There is not much literature on the impact of diet on normal bladder physiology, however, numerous studies are pointing to the role that diet has in the development of OAB, bladder outlet obstruction, LUTS and bladder cancer. This review examines the relationship between dietary macro/micro-nutrient choices and bladder physiology as well as the influence that dietary choices have regarding the incidence of various bladder pathophysiology.

Keywords: Bladder; physiology; diet; LUTS, overactive bladder, bladder obstruction

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INTRODUCTION

The bladder is a crucial component of the urinary system that serves as a storage area for urine until higher centers within the central nervous system initiates the micturition process. It is divided into 2 parts; a body and a base [1]. The bladder wall is made up of numerous smooth muscle fibers with individual cells integrally connected that are aligned in a variety of directions and are called detrusor muscle. The connection between the smooth muscle cells of the detrusor is strengthened by the presence of gap junctions and this helps it perform its major

function which is to contract during urination to void the contents of the bladder into the urethra. It also relaxes to allow for the storage of urine in the bladder [2]. The intertwining of smooth muscle cells and the formation of gap junctions also help in the rapid dissemination of signals from the nervous system to every bladder cell [1]. The base of the bladder controls the outflow of urine and is made up of the the trigone, anterior bladder walls, and vesicoureteral junction [3].

The autonomic nervous system determines if the bladder continues to store urine while it is still

relaxed, or if it contracts to expel urine [4]. Some level of conscious control over the release or continuous storage of urine in the bladder is also made possible through the somatic nervous system [5].

Dietary intake has an impact on a variety of metabolic and physiological processes and the cause and effect relationships between the diets which we consume and the etiology or prevention of diseases is being studied, although it is extremely challenging [6]. Diets are made up of macro and micro nutrients. Each macronutrient, consumed in large quantities; carbohydrate, protein, and fat, has its own set of health-promoting properties, but they all provide energy [7]. Micronutrients, particularly calcium, sodium, potassium, zinc, iron, vitamin D, and folic acid, are introduced in small amounts but are required for metabolic and physiologic processes [8]. A balanced diet contains all of the individual macronutrients (and micronutrients) essential for an individual's welfare and health [9]. The intake of a well-rounded diet is important as it has been observed that deficiency in one or more of the nutrients either macro or micro is linked to several non-communicable diseases [9].

Influence of Diets on Bladder Physiology

The content of diet has an impact on bladder function [10]. The effect of diets on smooth muscle function has been investigated and a strong association has been shown; with diets rich in calcium showing reducing effects on hypertrophy smooth muscle cells of the cardiac syncytium [10]. Diets rich in blueberries have also been shown to affect the contraction of vascular smooth muscle. It was seen that blueberries appear to affect vascular smooth muscle cells via endothelial mediator release, possibly involving the NO–cyclic GMP system. It was also reported that it prevented vascular smooth muscle contractions induced by α -adrenergic receptor agonists [11]. The detrusor muscle is a major constituent of the bladder and a large portion of this is made up of smooth muscle fibres that are longitudinal and circular [2]. Adedeji et al.,

hypothesized that dietary macronutrient composition of food could have an effect on detrusor smooth muscle hypertrophy and contraction in animals with normal bladders [10]. It was discovered that animals fed with high fat had a change in the overall morphology of their bladder; with an increase in bladder weight and thickness. Experiments to determine the contractile force of the detrusor of high fat diet (HFD) fed animals showed a reduction in contractile force in response to electrical stimulation [10]. All these show the negative high fat induced changes in the urinary bladder which could worsen with underlying disease conditions.

In another study by Adedeji and Olapade-Olaopa, it was reported that the constituents of diets affected a lot of growth factors and mediators that are involved in the inflammatory process and fibrosis in the bladder. High intake of diets high in fat was noted as the major dietary macronutrient that causes an elevation of these growth factors and mediators, leading to fibrosis and abnormal collagen composition of the bladder [12].

Dietary intake has been directly linked to conditions like obesity, with the combination of high carbohydrate and fat intake seen to increase the risk overweight and obesity [13]. Individuals with obesity are predisposed to developing metabolic syndrome as it is strongly linked to a lifestyle that includes easy access to an endless supply of high-calorie, low-nutrient-dense foods as well as physical inactivity [14]. Visceral obesity, dyslipidemia, glucose intolerance, insulin resistance, and hypertension are just a few of the metabolic risk factors that accompany metabolic syndrome, as well as its relation to lower urinary tract symptoms which has adverse effects on the bladder [9,10,15].

Dietary Factors Associated with Bladder Pathophysiology

Overactive Bladder

The International Continence Society defines an Overactive Bladder (OAB) as a condition with characteristic symptoms of “urinary urgency,

usually accompanied by frequency and nocturia, with or without urgency incontinence, in the absence of urinary tract infection or other obvious pathology” [16]. OAB is usually diagnosed in the absence of metabolic disorders, urinary stress incontinence, or urinary tract infection [17]. Although the cause of OAB in different individuals can vary from one person to another, each theory explains the overactivity of the detrusor muscle [17]. The afferent pathway of the bladder is affected by OAB syndrome and at a low bladder volume, there is usually a desire to void [18]. The detrusor muscle is richly supplied by a lot of nerves and only a partial denervation may cause muscle contractions that leads to a desire for urinary incontinence [18].

Overactive bladder is a common chronic condition that has been linked to a lower quality of life and there is an increasing body of evidence investigating the effect of diet on OAB [19]. In a study by Dallosso et al., where they investigated the effects of diets and other lifestyle factors on the incidence of OAB and it was reported that an increase in the consumption of vegetables reduced the risk of the onset of OAB [20]. The cohort study was conducted on 7046 community dwelling women and identified a positive correlation between obesity, carbonated soda consumption and overactive bladder symptoms. With the increased intake of high fat food, a predisposing factor for developing obesity, it has been implicated in the progression of overactive bladder symptoms [19]. The reduced risks noted with increased vegetable intake have been attributed to the many vitamins and minerals present in vegetables [20].

Independent studies by Adedeji et al., revealed that consumption of diets high in carbohydrate on the other hand, may cause bladder overactivity by increasing Ca^{2+} sensitization both directly and indirectly via Myosin Light Chain Kinase and Rho-kinase respectively which results in increased detrusor muscle contractility beyond normal [10].

Bladder Outlet Obstruction

Bladder outlet obstruction (BOO) is a disorder that is particularly prevalent among older males and it

results from a variety of functional or anatomic etiologies and it often produces lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) [10]. Symptoms of BOO could include reduced urinary stream, post voiding urinary dribbling, feeling of incomplete bladder emptying and hesitancy [21]. Functional obstruction can be caused by detrusor-sphincter dyssynergia (DSD), which affects the smooth muscle or the rhabdosphincter; primary bladder neck obstruction, which can be both functional and anatomic; or dysfunctional voiding, which is linked to learned voiding disorders or pelvic floor dysfunction linked to pain syndromes. The most common causes of anatomic obstruction in men are benign prostatic enlargement (BPH) and urethral stricture. Incontinence procedures are the most common cause of anatomic obstruction in women [21].

Adedeji et al., 2018 studied the effect of dietary macronutrients on animals with experimentally induced BOO. It was observed that animals with BOO fed with high fat and high protein diets had an increase in the weight and thickness of their bladder; hypertrophy of the bladder [10]. The high fat diet induced changes in the bladder morphology of the BOO animal's decreases detrusor's compensatory ability to expel urine against the obstruction which could be explained by a decrease in myosin content in hypertrophying smooth muscle [10]. The decrease in myosin content stated above is due to the inability of the rate of synthesis of myosin to be on par with the increasing smooth muscle volume of the detrusor; a result of hypertrophy due to high fat diet intake [22]. Rho Kinase I (ROK-I), Rho Kinase II (ROK-II) and Myosin Light Chain Kinase (MLCK) activity were observed to be elevated in BOO animals fed with high carbohydrate diet (HCD). Increase in MLCK activity occurs when there is an elevation in intracellular Ca^{2+} which causes calmodulin to be activated and causes the phosphorylation of myosin light chain (MLC) by MLCK, eventually, smooth muscle contraction occurs [23]. An increase in MLCK activity causes an increased detrusor tone and contractile activity which results in overactivity of the bladder; a compensatory mechanism for bladder outlet

obstruction and the enhanced contractile response [10].

The role of diet in bladder structure and function in BOO animals was displayed in a study by Adedeji et al., on Dietary reversal reverts diet-induced alterations in obstructed bladders of Wistar rats [24]. HD has been hypothesized to result in an increase in circulating free fatty acids, which would then mediate biological effects related to cell proliferation, triggering an increase in epithelial height and muscle fiber diameter of the detrusor and increased bladder weight [25]. Results from Adedeji et al., [24] however showed that a reversal of the diet of BOO animals from HFD to standard chow caused a significant reduction in bladder weight. The pronounced effects of high carbohydrate diet on BOO animals stated earlier also reversed after a switch from high carbohydrate diet to standard chow [24]. The study confirmed that dietary intake alters the structure and function of both normal and obstructed urinary bladders.

Urinary Incontinence

Urinary incontinence is an involuntary leakage of urine from the bladder that is majorly common in the elderly and has a major impact on the quality of life of an individual [26]. There are several forms of urinary incontinence. The involuntary leakage of urine accompanied with elevated intraabdominal pressure due to the weakness of the pelvic floor or urethral sphincter muscle is called stress urinary incontinence [27]. Due to the overactivity of the detrusor muscle, there can be an involuntary leakage of urine that is most times accompanied by a feeling of urinary urgency; this is called urge urinary incontinence [28]. Overflow urinary incontinence occurs due to an overstretched bladder [28]. The overdistension of the bladder is due to lack of detrusor contractility and BOO [28].

Priorities in research in urinary incontinence now include identifying lifestyle factors that can be modified [29]. One of the most easily modifiable lifestyle factor is diet [30]. A population based cross sectional study conducted by Maserejian et al., 2010 on 'Dietary Macronutrient and Energy Intake and

Urinary Incontinence in Women' revealed that individuals who had higher intake of saturated fatty acids had greater odds of urinary incontinence [31]. This was in corroboration with studies by Dalloso et al., [20] where the association of diet and stress incontinence was studied and they recorded an increase in urinary incontinence with increased HFD intake [20]. Incontinence as a result of higher HFD intake was adduced to endothelial dysfunction due to inflammation or vascular changes (a consequence of HFD consumption) affecting the bladder, detrusor, and urologic symptoms [32].

Bladder Cancer

Bladder cancer is a carcinoma of the urothelial cells that line the lumen of the urinary bladder [33]. It usually presents as visible hematuria but patients can also have isolated microscopic hematuria or irritative voiding symptoms [34]. It has been proposed that dietary factors may play a role in the development of bladder cancer because many diet-related metabolites come into direct contact with the bladder epithelium during excretion [35]. Studies by Allen et al., 2012 on 'Macronutrient intake and risk of urothelial cell carcinoma in the European prospective investigation into cancer and nutrition' revealed that high intake of energy from animal protein and a low intake of energy from plant protein is associated with an increased risk of bladder cancer [36]. While more research is needed to shed light the effects of dietary macronutrients on bladder cancer, this goes to show that dietary choices do have an impact.

CONCLUSION

The influence of diet on the body physiology cannot be overemphasized as content of diets can either positively or negatively affect normal body functions. Diet alters the structure and function of both normal and diseased bladders as shown above. The intake of HFD most especially causes major changes to the morphology and function of the bladder as it is implicated in major bladder pathophysiology such as BOO, urinary incontinence and OAB. Dietary interventions could therefore be a

major way of managing patients exhibiting these diseases. Further research however is required to clarify the association between various forms of diet and bladder physiology and pathophysiology.

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